

DOES SPORT PRACTICE AND DEVELOPMENTAL ENVIRONMENT IMPLY DIFFERENCES IN HAND SURFACE AREA MEASURED WITH HERON'S FORMULA?

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Abstract

Anthropometric assessment of the hand has many forms, some of which follow the size of finger lengths, fingertip distances, hand length and width, some circumferences or others. The objective of the present research is to propose a new variant of measuring hand area with Heron's formula. Testing of the hand area measurement method was done by studying 26 girls (18.95±0.48 years, 165.7±6.93 cm and 60.62±9.54 kg) and 97 boys (19.46±0.93 years, 177.8±6.28 cm and 74.77±11.23 kg). The determination of the area was done by drawing the landmarks of interest on a piece of paper and then dividing the covered polygon into triangles whose area was calculated with Heron's formula. The results showed that gender differentiates the area covered by the hand (girls: left–220.1±24 cm²; right–221.4±25.44 cm²; boys: left–261.7±26.76 cm²; right–258.6±27.67 cm²), while developmental environment and sport practice do not have the same effect, confirming our first hypothesis. The 2D/4D ratio of sport practitioners has values close to those of non-practitioners, refuting our second hypothesis. In young people, hand surface area is influenced by gender and less by developmental environment or sport practice. Playing a sport does not significantly change the 2D/4D ratio values. The proposed method can be used to quickly collect anthropometric information of athletes' hands and improved by modern technical means of measurement.

Keywords: Hand area, Heron formula, measuring, sport, urban, rural, 2D/4D

INTRODUCTION

Hand area has been determined in various ways, the most common measurement being the ratio of hand width to hand length. (Fallahi & Jadidian, 2011)

In sports games, where the ball is the object of work, the use of the hand is essential. Hand morphology and functional properties can be important for performance. (Barut, Demirel, & Kiran, 2008)

Measurement of hand surface area can be of great importance in the clinical field. A literature review conducted in 2013 (Rhodes, Clay, & Phillips, 2013) indicates numerous studies that are based on analysis of hand size and methods of hand assessment. The majority were noted to be from the field of plastic surgery and burn treatment, where the determination of burned skin surface area is paramount. Bansaghi and Haidegger (2020) used 6 methods to measure the size of the hand, the first of which is the most common and consists of measuring the width and length of the hand, based on drawing it on a white sheet while it had its fingers glued together.

Ruiz-Ruiz et al. (2002), followed the relationship between handgrip strength at different settings of the Jamar dynamometer and hand size, determined by measuring the distance between the ends of the hand with the fingers apart (distal phalanges of the pollicis and auricular). Measurements were rounded to the nearest value (e.g., 17=16.5-17.4 cm). Mirmohammadi et al. (2016) measured the hand dimensions of 529 workers in Iran and compared the values with those obtained in other studies, in which the subjects were workers, students, teachers. (Chandra, Chandna, & Deswal, 2011; Imrhan, Sarder, & Mandahawi, 2009;

Mandahawi, Imrhan, Al-Shobaki, & Sarder, 2008; Cakit, Durgun, Cetik, & Yoldas, 2014; Imrhan, Nguyen, & Nguyen, 1993) They assessed hand dimensions while fingers were glued: hand length, length of palmar region, hand width, width of 4 fingers (index, medius, ring, auricular), finger length, length of proximal, medial and distal phalanges, width of 5 distal interphalangeal joints, circumference of hand, wrist, fist and that formed between the wrist and medius. Fallahi and Jadidian (2011) used Visnapuu and Jürimäe's (2007) method of measuring the surface area of the hand, the outline of the hand was drawn on a white paper, with the fingers spread apart. Based on the drawing, the distances between the fingertips (from the tip of the thumb to the tip of each finger and from the tip of the thumb to the tip of the index, middle, ring and little finger) were determined, the lengths of the fingers (from the middle of the width formed by the styloid processes to the tip of each finger) and the perimeters formed by the centre of the width of the wrist and the tips of the fingers (centre-pole-index, centre-pole-medi- us, centre-index-medi- us, centre-medi- us-index- ring finger, centre-pole-index-medi- us-index-ring finger).

The size of the hand can be a reference when selecting a sport, especially if it involves handling an object with the hands. It is argued that the strength of the palmar flexors influences the athlete's ability to catch and throw the ball, but this variable is in turn conditioned by the size of the hand assessed. (Fallahi & Jadidian, 2011) The authors of a study establishing that the catching efficiency of athletes' working object (e.g., ball) is directly proportional to finger and hand

measurements. (Nag, 2003) Fallahi and Jadidian (2011) establishing that the distance drawn between the tips of the pollicis, index finger, medius, ring finger and auricular, the length of the index finger and the perimeter of the whole hand are correlated with palm flexor strength among basketball, handball, volleyball and wrestlers. They suggest that this information can be used in the talent identification process in sports where catching is important (handball, basketball, volleyball, baseball), but also in other sports such as wrestling, judo, climbing and rowing. In contrast, Cortell-Tormo et al. (2013) argue that the strength of the palmar flexors of judoka athletes depends on the values of the index and medius lengths and on the perimeter formed by center-medius-index-atrial-auricular-center.

It was also found that in sports where ball catching is ubiquitous, such as basketball and handball, the accuracy of throwing and handling the ball is better the longer the fingers of the hands. Based on this, Visnapuu and Jürimäe (2007) found that athletes with longer fingers and larger hand surface area also have a greater gripping ability. Kakaraparthi et al. (2022) concluded that there are correlations between palm flexor strength and hand area among schoolchildren aged 6-12 years.

España-Romero et al. (2008) found differences between the anthropometric values of 70 girls and 120 boys (17.2±1.4 cm vs. 17.8±1.5 cm; p=0.004), aged 6-12 years, in their study on the influence of hand size on the optimal grip duration of dynamometers for assessing palm flexor strength. Different values were also observed between male and female basketball players (left hand width: 76.85±7.77 mm vs. 73.69±5.75 mm; right hand width: 77.80±8.13 mm vs. 75.06±5.67 mm; left hand length: 173.84±18.11 mm vs. 167.94±12.70 mm; right hand length: 172.87±17.73 mm vs. 166.98±12.17 mm), volleyball (left hand width: 79.60±7.43 mm vs. 74.93±3.93 mm; right hand width: 80.17±7.64 mm vs. 76.41±4.15 mm; left hand length:

177.53±18.13 mm vs. 171.42±10.67 mm; right hand length: 176.77±18.42 mm vs. 170.97±10.25 mm) and handball (left hand width: 79.05±8.99 mm vs. 77.82±2.85 mm; right hand width: 80.09±9.20 mm vs. 78.92±3.12 mm; left hand length: 175.21±20.70 mm vs. 179.10±7.79 mm; right hand length: 174.54±19.83 mm vs. 179.00±8.22 mm). (Barut, Demirel, & Kiran, 2008)

Härkönen et al. (1993) evaluated 204 subjects to determine the relationship between hand anthropometry and palm flexor strength and found that the dimensions recorded by men were significantly higher compared to the values obtained by women, concluding that palm flexor strength is higher in men due to measurement.

We aim in this paper to present a novel method of measuring hand surface area using Heron's formula and presenting values for a sample of young men.

$$A_{triangle} = \sqrt{s(s-a)(s-b)(s-c)}, \quad \text{where}$$

$A_{triangle}$ —the area of the triangle, s —the half-perimeter $((a+b+c)/2)$, and a , b and c —the dimensions of its sides.

METHODS

The hands of 123 subjects (26 girls and 97 boys) were measured, whose characteristics are shown in Table 1. They are young Romanian students aged around 19 years old, the boys having higher height, weight and BMI than the girls. Each of them signed a voluntary participation agreement at the beginning, and the research received approval from the Scientific Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport in Iasi (no. 23/28.02.2023). Subjects declared by means of a form information related to gender, dominant hand, developmental background up to 18 years and concerns for practicing sport in a federally organized system.

Table 3

Anthropometric characteristics of the participants		
	Girls (N=26)	Boys (N=97)
Age (Years)	18.95±0.48	19.46±0.93
Height (Cm)	165.7±6.93	177.8±6.28****
Weight (Kg)	60.62±9.54	74.77±11.23****
BMI (Kg/M ²)	21.64±2.41	23.51±2.73***

Determination of hand dimensions was done by drawing the outline on A4 paper (Fig. 1) and measuring with a graduated ruler the proportions needed for the calculation. The subject placed the hand on the sheet of paper with the fingers fully extended and in a normal anatomical position, with the forearm on the table where the paper was placed. The assessor, with a pen, marked the outline of the following landmarks: the ulnar styloid process, the radial styloid process, the tip of each finger, the internal outline at the base of the fingers and the base of fingers 2 and 5. For ecological purposes, both hands were drawn on the same paper with different coloured pens (red and green). After drawing the outline, the landmarks needed for the measurement were marked for each hand.

The following distances were determined for each hand: ulnar styloid process-radial styloid process (a),

ulnar styloid process-fingertip 5 (b), ulnar styloid process-fingertip 4 (c), ulnar styloid process-fingertip 3 (d), radial styloid process-fingertip 3 (e), radial styloid process-fingertip 2 (f), radial styloid process-fingertip 1 (g), fingertip 5-fingertip 4 (h), fingertip 4-fingertip 3 (i), fingertip 3-fingertip 2 (j), fingertip 2-fingertip 1 (k). The marked marks allow the length of fingers 2 (l) and 4 (m) to be determined for the calculation of the 2D/4D ratio. All dimensions have been expressed in cm.

We propose calculating the area of the hand using Heron's formula, dividing the area of the polygon that can be covered into triangles whose area can be calculated separately. The triangles were numbered according to the sides they have: 1 (bch), 2 (cdi), 3 (ade), 4 (efj) and 5 (fgk).

Applying Heron's formula, after the a-k dimensions are known, the area covered by the hand can be

calculated according to the following formula:

$$A = \sqrt{s_1(s_1 - b)(s_1 - c)(s_1 - h)} + \sqrt{s_2(s_2 - c)(s_2 - d)(s_2 - i)} + \sqrt{s_3(s_3 - a)(s_3 - d)(s_3 - e)} +$$

$$\sqrt{s_4(s_4 - e)(s_4 - f)(s_4 - j)} + \sqrt{s_5(s_5 - f)(s_5 - g)(s_5 - k)},$$

where A—the area of the surface of the hand, s_x —the half-perimeter corresponding to triangle x, and a-k – the length of the sides of the triangles.

Figure 3 – Sketch of drawing of hands on paper

For ease of calculation, this can be done with MO Excel, using the SQRT function applied to the product of the semiperimeter and each of its differences from the sides.

The hypothesis testing of our study required the use of the Anova One-Way test. The aim was to identify the differences between the hand sizes of the measured subjects. GraphPad Prism 9.3.0 analysis software (GraphPad Software Inc.) identified the outliers and eliminated them for statistical processing of the data. The D’Agostino & Pearson test (D’Agostino & Pearson test) was then applied to check the normality of the distribution of the results, based on which the Anova One-Way processing settings were made. The significance threshold used was $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

The data obtained by hand measurement are systematized in Table 2. According to gender, developmental background and sport practice the 123 subjects were divided, each newly formed group having a result, expressed by arithmetic mean and standard deviation. The last column on the right shows the results of the Anova One-Way test applied to the three comparisons made. The significance of the comparison for each situation is below 0.001.

The first comparison of interest is that between girls and boys by side or dominance of hand use. The gender of the subjects generates a mean difference of about 39.4 cm², with boys having higher values, which is confirmed by the result of the statistical analysis ($F_{(7,484)}=25.72, p < 0.0001$).

Table 4

Hand surface area according to gender, developmental environment and sport practice

	Left hand area (cm ²)	Right hand area (cm ²)	Dominant hand area (cm ²)	Non-dominant hand area (cm ²)	Anova One-Way
Girls (n=26)	220.1±24	221.4±25.44	221.1±25.48	220.3±23.97	$F_{(7,484)}=25.72, p < 0.0001$
Boys (n=97)	261.7±26.76****	258.6±27.67****	258.3±27.45****	262±26.94****	
Urban girls (n=12)	222.5±25.92	228.8±20.69	228.2±21.03	223.1±25.78	$F_{(15,460)}=11.42, p < 0.0001$
Rural girls (n=14)	219.3±23.75	216.4±28.83	216.4±28.83	219.3±23.75	
Urban boys (n=52)	263.5±26.21	260.3±27.87	259.7±27.41	264.2±26.59	
Rural boys (n=45)	257±26.03	254.1±26.41	254.2±26.53	256.9±25.92	
Sport girls (n=6)	219±24.97	214.8±27.32	214.8±27.32	219±24.97	$F_{(15,464)}=12.56, p < 0.0001$
Non-sport girls (n=20)	220.4±24.36	223.3±25.24	223±25.32	220.7±24.31	
Sport boys (n=22)	268.3±23.22	267.7±24.75	268.2±24.60	267.9±23.38	
Non-sport boys (n=75)	258.6±26.68	254.9±27.39	254.4±27.03	259±26.96	

The subjects' developmental environment is related to the significance of differences given by Tukey's multiple comparisons test. Similar to the gender difference analysis, the groups formed (urban and rural boys and girls respectively) did not show differences between the sides, with the left (LDA) being as large as the right (RHA).

The difference was between girls and boys, with the latter having higher values ($F_{(15,460)}=11.42, p<0.0001$). The differences between the dominant hand (DHA= 228.2 ± 21.03 cm²) and the right hand (RHA= 228.8 ± 20.69 cm²) of urban girls and rural boys' hands were not significant, regardless of side (LHA and RHA) or dominance (DHA and NdHA) (Fig. 2).

Figure 4 – Differences in hand area given by gender and developmental environment (DHA–dominant hand area; NdHA–non-dominant hand area; RHA–right hand area; LHA–left hand area; urban–grown up in the urban environment; rural–grown up in the rural environment; G–girls; B–boys)

Practicing a sport does not imply any difference from those of the same gender who do not. Girls compared to boys have smaller palm areas according to hand side or dominance ($F_{(15,464)}=12.56, p<0.0001$). Tukey's multiple comparisons test shows a closeness of the non-dominant hand (NdHA) of girls practicing

sports to the non-dominant (NdHA) and right hand (RHA) of boys not practicing sports. The left hand (LHA) of the same girls is within insignificant difference of the right (RHA) and non-dominant (NdHA) hands of boys not involved in organised sport (Fig. 3).

Figure 5 – Differences in hand area given by gender and sport practice (DHA–dominant hand area; NdHA–non-dominant hand area; RHA–right hand area; LHA–left hand area; sport–sports practitioner; nonsport–not practicing sports; G–girls; B–boys)

Measures of the ratio of fingers 2 and 4 were compared with each other only for sports practitioners and non-sports practitioners. The results of the Anova One-

Way test ($F_{(7,228)}=0.54; p=0.80$) and Tukey's multiple comparisons test show close values for either girls, boys, dominant or non-dominant hand (Fig. 4).

Figure 6 – Differences in 2D/4D ratio given by gender and sport practice (DH–dominant hand; NdHA–non-dominant hand; sport–sports practitioner; nonsport–not practicing sports; G–girls; B–boys)

DISCUSSION

Our study proposes a new method to measure hand area based on mathematical calculations in which possible quantifiable dimensions are included. It is intended to be a pilot study on the basis of which to develop the possibility of collecting as much information as possible from a human individual by simply projecting the landmarks of his hand on a work tool (paper in our case) and subsequently determining them.

For this research we started from the high time requirement for measuring anthropometric characteristics with various instruments such as graduated ruler or digital caliper. Initially, the measurements were aimed at fingers 2 and 4 in order to achieve the ratio between them and estimate the degree of aggressiveness of the athletes. Later, the need arose to assess the growth of athletes by determining the size of their hands or feet.

The area covered by the hand could be of interest for sports involving the use of the hand on a larger playing surface: handball ($\approx 1135 \text{ cm}^2$), basketball ($\approx 1810 \text{ cm}^2$), volleyball ($\approx 1385 \text{ cm}^2$), American football, etc. Selection for these types of sport can be made on the basis of measured hand sizes.

Anthropometric differences between girls and boys have also been demonstrated in other studies that we join with our analysis. Our study sample has a balance between the sides, which obeys the principle of symmetrical development of the human body. At the same time, girls cover smaller areas with their hands compared to boys, making the difference significant. Whether we look at anatomical or dominant parts, bilateral differences are non-existent for the same category: girls or boys in urban/rural or sport practitioners/non-practitioners. Thus, environment and sport do not influence hand size by action or selection. There are some approximations of hand surfaces between girls and boys, depending on environment or sport practice, but that do not contribute to the process of confirming our hypotheses. The same effect is exerted on the 2D/4D ratio, which is similar for girls and boys, whether or not they play a sport. The comparison of hand surfaces confirms our first hypothesis that there is a difference between girls and boys, which cannot be influenced by their developmental environment or sport practice. At the same time, the 2D/4D ratio contradicts our assumption that it is lower in sports players, based

on the need for aggression in this respect. This refutes the second hypothesis of the study.

In one study, hand anthropometry was measured by 6 methods. For the first method a graduated ruler was used, in the second method the measurement was based on scanning the shape of the hand on paper, together with a 10 cm^2 reference mark, and digital editing of the scanned image by software that recorded the number of pixels of the hand surface. Method 3 consisted of photographing the palm region with the fingers glued together with the 10 cm^2 reference mark, and the width, length and size of the hand in pixels were determined. The 4th method was performed similarly to the previous one, except that the fingers of the assessed hand were spread apart. The 5th method consisted of scanning the hand and the reference mark simultaneously. For the last method the Semmelweis system was used, determining the hand dimensions based on the segmented images taken. (Bansaghi & Haidegger, 2020)

Our method having a high degree of novelty in the world of sport finds it difficult to relate to other values in the literature.

Barut et. al. (2008) established differences between basketball, handball and volleyball players in terms of hand dimensions among both girls and boys. Significant discrepancies were noted between basketball and handball hand shape indices (left: 44.32 ± 2.08 vs. 45.12 ± 1.73 ; right: 45.01 ± 2.17 vs. 45.89 ± 1.73). Among girls, handball players differed from volleyball and basketball players by larger width values (left: 77.82 ± 2.85 vs. 74.93 ± 3.93 vs. 73.69 ± 5.75 mm); right: 78.92 ± 3.21 vs. 76.41 ± 4.15 vs. 75.06 ± 5.67 mm) and lengths of both hands (left: 179.10 ± 7.79 vs. 171.42 ± 10.67 vs. 167.94 ± 12.70 mm; right: 179.00 ± 8.22 vs. 170.97 ± 10.25 vs. 166.98 ± 12.17 mm).

Overall, handball players had much larger hand widths compared to the other 2 disciplines, but the biggest difference was with basketball players (left: 78.86 ± 8.34 mm vs. 75.55 ± 7.15 mm; right: 79.91 ± 8.54 mm vs. 76.67 ± 7.32 mm).

The results of our research are of interest to sports practitioners who can use the measurement method in the selection of athletes at any level of performance, especially in sports that involve handling an object.

CONCLUSIONS

Our hand measurement method is different from existing methods, having the advantage of quickly collecting a lot of information from subjects for whom knowledge of hand dimensions is desired.

There are significant differences in hand sizes between girls and boys, even if the analysis is done for anatomical or dominant parts.

Developmental environment and sport practice do not influence the surface area covered by the palms, the differences for these criteria are only generated by the gender of the subjects. The first hypothesis was confirmed.

Aggression indicated by the low 2D/4D ratio shows insignificant differences between sports players, which refutes our second hypothesis.

The prospect of a faster determination of the hand surface may be to scan the hand and determine the necessary dimensions with software that has measurement options (e.g. Photoshop).

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